

CHEMISTRY OF VASICINE AND CHAKSINE*

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VASICINE AND PEGANINE

It was in 1926 that I was asked by Acharya Ray to investigate the active principles of *Vasaka*. Extract *Vasaka* was one of the first items to be put in the market by Bengal Chemical & Pharmaceutical Works. In the indigenous system of medicine, *Vasaka* enjoyed a great reputation as an expectorant and, in fact, claims have been made that it has antitubercular properties. While I was engaged in isolating the alkaloid, Sen and Ghose¹ isolated vasicine, $C_{11}H_{12}ON_2$, a monoacid base. They found it to be converted to chlorodesoxyvasicine with PCl_5 , indicating that there was an OH group, replaceable by Cl. With permanganate, a substance, $C_8H_8NO_2$, was isolated. This was suspected to be 4-oxyquinazoline. Later on, Ghose, Krishna, Narang and Ray² proved this supposition to be correct by a direct comparison of the oxidation product with synthetic 4-oxyquinazoline. Sen and Ghose¹ had assigned a structure in which vasicine was visualised as 2-propyl (or isopropyl)-4-oxyquinazoline, but De and Ray³ proved that vasicine was not identical with the products synthesised as follows :

Ghose, Krishna, Narang and Ray³ found evidence that vasicine was converted into an isomeric substance with alkali, but later on withdrew the claim as they were not sure about the purity of the transformation product⁴. They found³ that vasicine gave a solid dehydro-acetyl derivative, m.p. 165°.

In 1934, Späth and Nikawitz⁵ were supplied by the firm of E. Merck a base isolated from the mother-liquors of *Peganum harmala* from which they isolated a crystalline product having the same empirical composition as vasicine, which they called peganine. The base melted at about 5° higher than vasicine, but its m.p. was determined in vacuo as it, like vasicine, decomposed on melting. But it was stated that peganine gave a liquid acetyl derivative; hence doubts were expressed by us about the identity of vasicine and peganine. We were not able to secure a specimen of peganine from Vienna. The solubility of vasicine in acetone also differed from peganine. Hanford, Liang and Adams⁶ who found the solubility of vasicine in acetone to be small, as found by the Indian workers, also confirmed that the acetyl derivative was not a liquid, but a solid, having the same m.p. as found by us. Späth *et al.* later on agreed that the acetyl derivative was a solid. Finally Späth and Kuffner⁷ definitely

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established the identity of the two by direct comparison with a sample supplied from India.

Späth and Nikawitz⁴ found that on oxidation of vasicine with permanganate at low temperature, it gave 4-oxyquinazoline-*N*-acetic acid. On this basis they formulated vasicine as:

It may be pointed out that the Indian workers, who had earlier isolated 4-oxyquinazoline as the oxidation product, had stated that the isolation of 4-oxyquinazoline did not mean that an oxygen atom pre-existed in this position, as quinazolines were known to acquire an oxygen atom in this position during oxidation. This observation of theirs proved to be correct as subsequently it was found that vasicine did not have an oxygen atom in the second ring.

Narang and Ray⁵ criticised the Späth formula on various grounds, but mainly because of the fact that 3-allyl-1:3-benzodiazine was not identical with desoxyvasicine, and the reduction product of 3-allyl-4-oxyquinazoline with Na and amyl alcohol was not identical with the similar reaction product of vasicine.

Reynolds and Robinson⁶ adduced further proof against the Späth formula and suggested that in view of prior isolation of vasicine, the name peganine should be abandoned. The späth formula depicted vasicine as a carbinol-amine, but it showed no reactions of this class of substances.

The first suggestion, apart from the suggestion of Ghose *et al.*² that there was a third ring in *isovasicine*, was that of Hanford *et al.*⁶ The presence of an allyl group was never seriously suggested by us. The evidence pointing to this direction was the decolorisation of permanganate by vasicine at 0°, but as against this has to be stated the fact that the reduction of the so-called allyl group is never possible either catalytically or by other means. Vasicine has no rotation, but Ghose *et al.*² were able to resolve it, showing that one of the atoms was asymmetric. This result was later confirmed by Späth although they criticised Ray *et al.*¹⁷ for not publishing the full details of the resolution. This we would have done as soon as optically pure samples

of enantiomorphs had been obtained. The active forms showed signs of auto-racemisation and, hence, full details were withheld by us for a time. At this stage it was agreed by all the contestants that vasicine had a system of 3 ring systems fused together. We had proved the existence of the quinazoline ring by isolating 4-oxyquinazoline first. Thus the novelty of a quinazoline in a plant product was established. The isolation of 4-oxyquinazoline-*N*-acetic acid was undoubtedly an advance, but this had led Späth to rashly postulate the position of the oxygen atom to be OH in the β -position in the third ring. Späth postulated all the possible formulae with 3 rings—one of them was sure to be correct in the long run. In the mean time, Indian workers proceeded on to establish whether the third ring was fused linearly or angularly. Narang and Ray¹⁰ prepared the following and found that the reduction of the linearly fused ring was identical with the electrolytically reduced product of vasicine.

Therefore the nature of all the rings of vasicine had been understood and established. The Indian workers¹¹ pleaded for a little time to complete the investigation which they had begun much earlier than the Austrian workers. The Americans withdrew from the field but the Austrians won the race.

The synthesis of desoxyvasicine by Späth *et al.* is at best at par with the work of the Indian workers and only proves the linear configuration of the third ring. It does not indicate the position of the OH group. Morris, Hanford and Adams¹² furnished an acceptable proof of the position of the OH group. They proved that it was in the α -position and not in β -position, as supposed by the Austrian workers. Now the way was paved for the final synthesis of vasicine. This was a comparatively simple matter as all the details about vasicine were now known to all. The race again was won by the Austrians who condensed *o*-nitrobenzyl chloride with α -hydroxyaminobutyric acid. The product on cyclisation and reduction furnished vasicine.

CHAKSINE

It was in 1935, Siddiqui and Ahmed¹⁴ isolated a quaternary base from the seeds of *Cassia absus* and assigned the formula $C_{12}H_{20}O_2N_3.OH$. But Ray *et al.*¹¹ suggested that the base should be formulated as $C_{11}H_{20}O_2N_3.OH$ and adduced evidence in support of this view. After a long controversy it is now agreed by all that the formula of Lahore workers is correct¹⁵. Guha and Ray¹⁶ assigned a tentative structure for chaksine after studying a large number of its degradation products. They relied mostly on I.R. of several of chaksine derivatives. The salient absorptions were in the regions noted below :

6.35 m μ	presence of C=N	(formerly questioned by Singh <i>et al.</i> , ²¹ but now admitted to be correct).
3.0 m μ	,, ,, NH	(This NH was supposed to be a part of a ureido group absorption at 5.8 and 5.95m μ).
7.22 m μ	,, ,, C—Me.	
5.80 m μ	,, ,, CO conjugated ester.	
5.95 } m μ	,, ,, CO-NH.	
6.10 }		
7.62 } m μ	,, ,, $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \parallel \\ \text{C—NH—C} \end{array}$	
7.86 }		

No proof was given for the bicyclic ring system except that the acids obtained by hydrolysis with baryta on distillation afforded pyrrole. It was recognised that this was a vulnerable point of the formula suggested.

Kamal and Hahn¹⁸ found that when chaksine was heated with alkali, 2 mols. of ammonia were evolved progressively: the first mol. in 40 hours and the second in 240 hours. Therefore it will be seen that the third N atom is differently constituted from the two others. In assigning a structure to chaksine, this fact has to be borne in mind. Kamal and Hahn¹⁸ have also confirmed the transformation of chaksine nitrate to nitrochaksine, observed and described by Ray *et al.*¹⁹. The latter authors were aware of the possibility of this transformation also being of the type guanidine nitrate to nitroguanidine and had indicated this possibility years ago¹⁹. They gave up this idea in view of some of the model guanidine compounds synthesised at Lahore not behaving at all like chaksine. The I.R. absorption at 5.95, 6.10, 7.62, 7.85 m μ , all pointed out an urea residue being present in chaksine.

Guha and Ray¹⁹ from the I. R. evidence concluded that probably a COOH was present in the nitrochaksine molecule. This was hotly contested by Singh *et al.*²⁰; but Kamal and Hahn¹⁸ found nitrochaksine to be amphoteric, which definitely did not rule out the possibility of a COOH being set free from a lactone ring rendered unstable. We have now found definite evidence that there is a lactone (lactide) ring in chaksine. If chaksine is heated with ammonium acetate (sulphate or chloride can be taken), and then the mixture is diluted with water, a clear solution results. From this on acidification a substance, different from chaksine sulphate, is precipitated. Preliminary

results show it to have CO.NH_2 group and CH_2OH formed by the opening of a

Singh *et al.*²¹ by treatment with alkali isolated, from chaksine, methylpimelic acid and chaksine acid. The latter has now been formulated as 1:2:6-heptane tricarboxylic acid²¹.

Siddiqui *et al.*¹⁸ have found that by distillation of chaksine with electrolytic Cu, phthalic acid is formed. The aromatic ring has been formed no doubt by pyrolysis, but this proves that 8 C atoms are in a chain.

Very recently a group of American authors²² have formulated chaksine as (I).

(I)

We feel that such a structure is improbable on many grounds as it does not satisfactorily account for the formation of *isopropylbenzoic acid*, α -pimelic acid, phthalic acid etc. The reliance on I.R. for a cyclic urea structure may not be reliable.

We think that in view of (a) the difference between the third N and the other two, (b) liberation of CO_2 from chaksine on heating with HCl, (c) formation of phthalic acid on pyrolysis, (d) formation of methylpimelic acid (this needs confirmation) and (e) 1:2:6-heptane tricarboxylic acid, chaksine can be represented as :

X may be attached to (1) or to (10). The atoms No. 1, 2 and 6 are involved in an intra-annular tautomerism. There may be H bonding between atom No. 6 and No. 1. Chaksine gives HCHO with Fenton's reagent, suggesting the linkage of X at 10.

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